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RESEARCH-ARTICLE

Reconsidering Fairness Through Unawareness From the Perspective of Model Multiplicity

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Reconsidering Fairness Through Unawareness From the Perspective of Model Multiplicity

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Abstract

Fairness through Unawareness (FtU) describes the idea that discrimination against demographic groups can be avoided by not considering group membership in the decisions or predictions. This idea has long been criticized in the machine learning literature as not being sufficient to ensure fairness. In addition, the use of additional features is typically thought to increase the accuracy of the predictions for all groups, so that FtU is sometimes thought to be detrimental to all groups. In this paper, we show both theoretically and empirically that FtU can reduce algorithmic discrimination without necessarily reducing accuracy. We connect this insight with the literature on Model Multiplicity, to which we contribute with novel theoretical and empirical results. Furthermore, we illustrate how, in a real-life application, FtU can contribute to the deployment of more equitable policies without losing efficacy. Our findings suggest that FtU is worth considering in practical applications, particularly in high-risk scenarios, and that the use of protected attributes such as gender in predictive models should be accompanied by a clear and well-founded justification.

CCS Concepts

• **Theory of computation** → **Theory and algorithms for application domains**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Learning linear models**; *Supervised learning*; *Philosophical/theoretical foundations of artificial intelligence*.

Keywords

Machine Learning, Model Multiplicity, Rashomon, Fairness, Logistic Regression, Disparate Impact

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1 Introduction

Nurtured by the ever-increasing availability of data and compute, as well as a widespread fondness of quantification in general [37] and Big Data in particular [8], machine learning-based systems

are increasingly used to assist decision making in a variety of areas of society, including in high-stakes domains such as healthcare, finance, law enforcement, and the provision of social services. Leveraging data is often seen not only as a way to improve decisions but also as a way to avoid human bias and enhance objectivity and fairness. However, there is mounting evidence of a variety of problems that can arise in different contexts as a result of this trend [45]. One such problem is unintended algorithmic discrimination, which can arise for different reasons, including biased training data, flawed model assumptions, unequal representation of different demographic groups, or misuse of the models. As a result, algorithmic decisions may systematically disadvantage certain individuals or communities grouped by their protected attributes, such as gender, race, age, or religion. These concerns have prompted a substantial body of research focused on understanding, detecting, and mitigating algorithmic biases [3]. A seemingly straightforward approach to preventing algorithmic discrimination across groups is the exclusion of protected attributes from the set of features that the model can “see”. This idea is known as *Fairness through Unawareness* or FtU [3]. However, the algorithmic fairness literature has shown that avoiding the use of protected attributes in the models is generally not sufficient to prevent discrimination [10, 34]: other variables can encode group membership information and thus their use could lead to discrimination. Furthermore, FtU is often criticized not only for being an unreliable approach to achieve fairness, but also for potentially reducing the predictive performance of the model for all groups [13].¹

Such results align with a common intuition in the Big Data era: that more data (and attributes) lead to better, fairer, and more objective decisions [8]. A recent practical example of this way of thinking can be found in Austria, where gender was used as an input in an algorithm designed to allocate job training programs to unemployed individuals. Officials dismissed criticisms regarding potential discriminatory outcomes by arguing that the algorithm’s predictions reflect the actual chances individuals face in the labour market (as cited in Allhutter et al. [1]). More generally, many arguments in favour of including protected attributes rely on the idea that machine learning models aim to estimate “true” probabilities from data, which is a questionable assumption [26]. As a result of this assumption, modelling choices may be accepted with limited scrutiny or justification, despite their significant implications [33]. However, there is growing evidence that policy outcomes are highly sensitive to modelling decisions, including the choice of thresholds, input variables, and specific design parameters [2, 27]. In parallel, emerging research on *model multiplicity* highlights that different models trained on the same data can perform similarly in terms

¹Such a reduction in accuracy need not lead to a reduction in utility [12].

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of accuracy, yet differ substantially in their behaviour, particularly with respect to fairness [7]. This perspective highlights that there is no clear hierarchy between models in terms of accuracy and that modelling choices need to be checked against alternative choices.

In light of these concerns, we revisit the commonly held scepticism toward *Fairness through Unawareness* (FtU). While we do not suggest that FtU offers a simple solution to achieve algorithmic fairness, we demonstrate that, contrary to prevailing assumptions, omitting protected attributes does not necessarily harm predictive performance and can contribute to more equitable outcomes. To substantiate these claims, we analyse the relationship between data, model class, and fairness, both from a theoretical and from an empirical perspective. While we derive general insights, we place particular emphasis on logistic regression because of its broad and extensive use in practice to build models from tabular data. Regarding fairness, we focus on disparate impact (DI) or statistical/demographic parity, which compares the positive classification rates for different groups according to their protected attribute. Our findings suggest that including protected attributes can be especially problematic in the context of logistic regression, as their use by such models can easily exacerbate disparities between protected groups. By linking the concepts of FtU and model multiplicity, we argue for a shift in perspective: fairness should not be seen as a constraint or a trade-off, but as a deliberate modelling choice that can lead to more equitable outcomes without necessarily sacrificing predictive performance.

In sum, the main **contributions** of this work are as follows:

- We analyse the relationship between disparate impact and base rate difference in the data both for any classifier and for logistic regression. In the case of logistic regression, we demonstrate the risk of exacerbated unfairness depending on the classification thresholds.
- We contribute to the understanding of model multiplicity and algorithmic fairness by providing mathematical results that characterise the potential for multiplicity and connect it to fairness: (1) general upper bounds on model multiplicity and changes in disparate impact which are tight for unconstrained models; and (2) lower bounds on achievable reductions in disparate impact based on FtU for logistic regression.
- We empirically demonstrate how unaware models can yield similar levels of accuracy than aware models with significant improvements in fairness in multiple settings.
- We highlight the practical implications on our work by discussing a real-world example related to employment programs in a European country.

The **structure** of this article is as follows. In Section 2, we provide an overview of related work on fairness, less discriminatory alternatives, and model multiplicity. In Section 3, we highlight the importance of modelling choices by demonstrating that there is no straightforward connection between disparate impact and differences in base rates, even assuming well-calibrated models. We also show that disparate impact can often be higher than the base rate difference for *aware* models (*i.e.* models using protected attributes), especially for models based on logistic regression. In Section 4, we frame our work from the perspective of model multiplicity. We

provide new theoretical upper bounds and relate them to disparate impact and to fairness through unawareness. In the case of logistic regression, we also provide theoretical lower bounds for reducing disparate impact. We illustrate our insights empirically in Section 5, showing that FtU can provide fairer models with almost equal accuracy across multiple datasets, protected attributes, and model classes. Section 6 illustrates the impact of our work in a real-world scenario where an aware logistic regression model was used to assign unemployed individuals to job training programs. We show how in this case an unaware model would be equally performative but fairer. Finally, the main conclusions and lines of future work are described in Section 7.

2 Related work

2.1 Algorithmic fairness and disparate impact

Under the influence of legal, economic, and philosophical notions of discrimination as well as several high-profile investigations into existing software, an extensive body of work on algorithmic fairness has introduced a variety of metrics to quantify and address discrimination in machine learning systems [3]. One line of work focuses on error rate disparities, *i.e.*, the differences in false positive or false negative rates across demographic groups. However, some scholars have argued that error rates should serve as *diagnostic tools* rather than direct targets for fairness interventions [3]. Another influential line of work draws on legal and policy traditions, particularly anti-discrimination law in the United States, introducing the concept of *disparate impact*—also referred to in the machine learning literature as *demographic or statistical parity* [4, 21]. Disparate Impact focuses on algorithmic outcomes rather than errors: it compares the rates at which individuals from different demographic groups receive positive classifications (*e.g.*, job offers, university admissions, loan approvals). If one group consistently receives favourable outcomes at a lower rate than other groups, this may be evidence of systemic bias.² While disparate impact has the advantage of aligning closely with legal standards and public perceptions, it also faces criticism, particularly in machine learning contexts. Enforcing strict parity in classification outcomes may lead to a reduction in accuracy and thus overall “utility” [24], especially when base rates differ across groups. This trade-off can result in decisions that, while statistically balanced, may harm individuals or reduce efficiency without delivering clear benefits [13]. Moreover, socio-technical critiques point out that measures such as disparate impact that focus on classification rates, just like error-focused measures, only consider model properties and may fail to result in just outcomes when actually deployed [28, 40]. Nonetheless, disparate impact has a more straightforward connection to the real-world consequences of models than error rates. In this work, we assume that reducing disparate impact is often desirable as long as it does not imply a notable reduction in accuracy, broadly in line with calls for non-ideal approaches to fairness [20] and comparative (rather than transcendental) approaches to justice [42]. Indeed, this perspective reflects the original motivation behind the notion of disparate impact; in contrast, its criticism in algorithmic fairness often

²These outcome disparities are sometimes quantified by means of the *disparate impact ratio* and evaluated using heuristics like the “80% rule”—which, however, is only a “crude test” [38].

concerns the full elimination of disparate impact, which reflects its common treatment as a mathematical formula that is exchangeable with other metrics.

2.2 Less discriminatory alternatives and model multiplicity

In legal doctrine under U.S. anti-discrimination law, the concept of disparate impact is closely related to the idea of a *Less Discriminatory Alternative*: a policy or decision-making process that leads to disparate impact can be justifiable as long as there exists no alternative that meets the same legitimate objectives while producing less discriminatory outcomes. This principle plays a central role in Title VII of the Civil Rights Act and has informed a wide range of employment and civil rights cases [4]. In the context of machine learning, less discriminatory alternatives can be operationalized as a fairness-aware criterion for model selection: if two models perform similarly regarding predictive accuracy but one model has lower disparate impact than the other, the fairer model could be considered as the less discriminatory alternative and thus would be both ethically preferable and potentially legally required in regulated environments [4].

Although central to disparate impact, the concept of less discriminatory alternatives has only recently gained attention in the ML literature, particularly in the context of *model multiplicity* (MM) [6, 23]. MM describes the phenomenon where multiple different models can achieve comparable accuracy on the same task. While the underlying idea—sometimes called *Rashomon effect*—has been known for decades [9], only in recent years has it become a focus of systematic investigation [31]. Despite promising recent work [41], this area of research is still in its early stages.

An intriguing aspect of MM is that models with similar accuracy can exhibit very different behaviours regarding robustness, fairness, or interpretability [7, 15, 39]. By virtue of MM, it is often possible to select fairer models without losing accuracy, *i.e.* less discriminatory *algorithms* (LDAs) [5]. In such cases, the existence of accurate and fairer alternatives underscores the need to examine the modelling pipeline beyond aggregate performance metrics. From a fairness perspective, MM implies that selecting one model over another is not only a neutral performance-based decision, as it can have a differential real-world impact across demographic groups. In this paper, we investigate how Fairness through Unawareness (FuU) can, in some cases, provide a less discriminatory alternative without requiring explicit fairness optimisation, which has been investigated in other works [15, 23]. We examine whether models that exclude protected attributes from their input can still maintain competitive predictive performance while reducing disparate impact, particularly in the context of logistic regression, a widely used model in real-world scenarios.

3 Calibrated aware models can exacerbate inequality

“Predictive models trained with supervised learning methods are often good at calibration [...] But calibration also means that by default, we should expect our models to faithfully reflect disparities found in the input data.” [3, p. 21]

Reflected in this quote from the most prominent textbook on algorithmic fairness is the frequent assumption that disparities present in the data will be carried over into calibrated machine learning models by default. While this assumption may hold true for probabilistic models, it does not apply to classifiers derived from these models. In this section, we demonstrate that, perhaps counterintuitively, decisions based on calibrated probabilities can actually worsen the inequalities reflected in the base rates of labels. We also show that this effect is especially pronounced in policies relying on logistic regression models.

We assume an input space \mathcal{X} and a, possibly empirical, joint probability distribution P over random variables (X, Y) which can take binary values in $\mathcal{X} \times \{0, 1\}$. Take a predictor $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and a corresponding classifier

$$F : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}, x \mapsto \mathbb{1}[f(x) \geq 0.5]. \quad (1)$$

Assume two groups that form a partition $\{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}$ of \mathcal{X} .³ The purpose of this section is to analyse how the disparate impact (DI)

$$\text{DI}(F) := \mathbb{E}_P[F(X) \mid X \in \mathcal{A}] - \mathbb{E}_P[F(X) \mid X \in \mathcal{B}] \quad (2)$$

relates to the difference in base rates (DBR)

$$\text{DBR} := \mathbb{E}_P[Y \mid X \in \mathcal{A}] - \mathbb{E}_P[Y \mid X \in \mathcal{B}]. \quad (3)$$

In this paper, we assume that \mathcal{B} is the disadvantaged group, *i.e.*, $\text{DBR} \geq 0$.

3.1 General case

The first observation is that for calibrated predictors, the label rates in the data are reflected in the means of the predictors. In the standard sense of Chouldechova [11], a predictor f is *calibrated* on both groups if

$$\forall v \in [0, 1], * \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\} : \mathbb{E}_P[Y \mid f(X) = v, X \in *] = v. \quad (4)$$

Now, if f is calibrated in this sense, then the average prediction of f on either group trivially equals the average outcome for that group (simply by integrating over v):

$$\forall * \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\} : \mathbb{E}_P[f(X) \mid X \in *] = \mathbb{E}_P[Y \mid X \in *]. \quad (5)$$

While all predictors that are calibrated on a given dataset will have the same mean, equal to the base rate, these different predictors can lead to different classification rates. We illustrate this with a simple toy example.

EXAMPLE 1. Take $\mathcal{X} = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4\}$ with P defined via $\forall x \in \mathcal{X} : P(x) = 0.25$ and $P(Y = 1 \mid X = x) = 0.4, 0.4, 0.55, 0.7$ for $x = x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4$, respectively. Then the predictors f_1, f_2, f_3 as defined in Table 1a are all calibrated in the standard sense (without groups) while leading to very different classifications (Table 1b).

We turn next to the quantities of interest: disparate impact and difference in base rates. First, we consider the most general case, with arbitrary f , α , and P . It is important to note that disparate impact depends on the ratio of predictions above/below the decision threshold, whereas the base rate difference depends on the means of the predictions (assuming calibration). We can formalise this in

³This is the case when the input features contain a protected attribute encoding group membership, *i.e.*, for group-aware models.

a	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4
$p(x)$	0.4	0.4	0.55	0.7
$f_1(x)$	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.7
$f_2(x)$	0.475	0.55	0.475	0.55
$f_3(x)$	0.5125	0.5125	0.5125	0.5125
b	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4
$B(x)$	0	0	1	1
$F_1(x)$	0	0	0	1
$F_2(x)$	0	1	0	1
$F_3(x)$	1	1	1	1

Table 1: Top (table a): Calibrated predictors for Example 1, where $p(x) = P(Y = 1 | X = x)$ is the true probability. f_1 is given by joining x_3 with x_1 and x_2 ; f_2 given by joining x_1 with x_3 and joining x_2 with x_4 ; f_3 is given by the constant base rate predictor. All of these predictors are calibrated. Bottom (table b): Classifiers derived by the models in table a, where B is the Bayes optimal classifier.

terms of the distributions of the predictions for each group, P_A and P_B , where

$$P_*(v) := P(f(X) = v | X \in *) \quad \text{for } v \in [0, 1], * \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}. \quad (6)$$

Then, for random variables $V_a, V_b \sim P_A, P_B$ describing the group-wise predictions, the disparate impact is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DI}(F) &= P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}) - P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B}) \\ &= P_{\mathcal{A}}(\{V_a \geq 0.5\}) - P_{\mathcal{B}}(\{V_b \geq 0.5\}) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and the difference in base rates by

$$\text{DBR} = \mathbb{E}_{P_A}[V_a] - \mathbb{E}_{P_B}[V_b]. \quad (8)$$

The difference in base rates can intuitively be understood as the balance of how much and how far the probability mass is moved to the left vs the right of the decision boundary when moving from P_B to P_A .⁴ The disparate impact, on the other hand, only depends on the balance of how much probability mass passes over the decision threshold.

The base rate difference and the disparate impact can be directly related under specific conditions, for example, when P_A is higher on one side of the threshold and P_B is higher on the other (proofs can be found in Appendix B):

PROPOSITION 1 (RELATION BETWEEN BASE RATES AND DISPARATE IMPACT). *Assume f is calibrated as in (4), satisfying $\forall v \in [0, 0.5) : P_B(v) \geq P_A(v)$ and $\forall v \in [0.5, 1] : P_A(v) \geq P_B(v)$. Then for F defined as in (1), $\text{DI}(F) \geq \text{DBR}$.*

3.2 Special case: Logistic Regression

We now investigate the relationship between disparate impact and the difference in base rates in the case of logistic regression. Logistic regression is a widely used type of statistical method for modelling the probability of a binary outcome based on one or more predictor variables. Its popularity is due to its simplicity, interpretability, and

⁴This means that if P_A ‘dominates’ P_B in the sense of $\exists T : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $T(v) \geq v \forall v \in [0, 1]$ s.t. $T(V_b) \sim P_A$, then the base rate difference equals the earth mover (Wasserstein-1) distance.

Figure 1: Plot of the sigmoid function used in logistic regression. Note that the slope is steepest around $z = 0$ and satisfies $\sigma(0) = 0.5$.

effectiveness in tackling classification problems. The model class consists of linear models with a sigmoid output σ ,

$$f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [0, 1], (x_1, \dots, x_n) \mapsto \sigma \left(c_0 + \sum_i c_i x_i \right) \quad (9)$$

with $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and the sigmoid function defined by $\sigma : z \mapsto \frac{1}{1+e^{-z}}$.

Training a logistic regression model consists of finding the values of the model’s coefficients $c_0, \dots, c_n \in \mathbb{R}$ that best fit the data by minimising a logistic loss function (equivalent to maximising the likelihood) using optimisation techniques like gradient descent. If a protected attribute is part of the input space, there will be a corresponding coefficient $c_i \in \mathbb{R}$ which determines how the protected attribute affects the (pre-sigmoid) logit function, $\hat{f}(x) := c_0 + \sum_i c_i x_i$. Therefore, for binary protected attributes where x_i can be 0 or 1, being part of the disadvantaged group ($x_G = 1$) implies adding a term c_G to the logit without further interaction with the rest of the variables.

We focus on the case where $P(Y | X, G = *)$ differs significantly between groups, as this makes the existence of a fixed global coefficient c_G particularly problematic.⁵ A difference in base rates means that, if the model is calibrated for both groups (5), the coefficient of the variable that corresponds to the group attribute will penalise all members of the disadvantaged group because the coefficient for that group will reduce the logit by a fixed value c_G , before applying the sigmoid, which can then contribute to an even larger disparate impact. To understand why, consider the shape of the sigmoid function displayed in Figure 1: The curve is steeper around the classification threshold at $\sigma(z) = 0.5$ than for other values of z , as highlighted by the red lines. Therefore, small changes in z near the classification threshold would lead to significant changes in the value of the sigmoid.

Consider the following example with a logistic regression classifier: Two individuals have feature vectors x^b and x^a that are identical except for their group membership, such that person b belongs to group \mathcal{B} and person a belongs to group \mathcal{A} . Therefore, the only element that differs between the two individuals’ predictions is the coefficient corresponding to the variable that denotes which group they belong to. Changes in this coefficient will shift the logit

⁵In the case where $P(Y | X, G = *)$ is the same across groups but $P(X | G = *)$ is different, the choice of model class may not have as immediate an effect. However, this choice still affects the resulting predictive distribution, which has an effect on the disparate impact as shown above.

value z . Imagine the output of the logistic regression function (predicted probabilities) for each of them is $\sigma(z^b) = 0.95$ and $\sigma(z^a) = 0.9$. To obtain the logit values z^a and z^b , we need to apply the inverse sigmoid $z = \sigma^{-1}(p) = \ln(\frac{p}{1-p})$. In the example, $\sigma^{-1}(0.95) \approx 2.94$ and $\sigma^{-1}(0.90) \approx 2.20$, such that their difference is ≈ 0.75 . This difference comes from the assumed difference in base rates between groups in this example. This suggests that group \mathcal{A} has a group offset that raises the logit by 0.75 when compared to group \mathcal{B} for the same input features. Now, let's consider an individual in group \mathcal{B} that has a predicted probability right at the classification threshold at $\sigma(z) = 0.5$ (therefore, logit $z = 0$); and another individual with exactly the same feature vector but belonging to group \mathcal{A} . The logit would increase by 0.75 because of the group effect, such that $z_a = z_b + 0.75 = 0 + 0.75$, $\sigma(0.75) \approx 0.68$. This means that the same features lead to higher predictions for members of \mathcal{A} due to the group offset: for every individual in group \mathcal{A} with scores between 0.5 and 0.68, there is a counterpart in \mathcal{B} who would fall below the threshold, even though their other features are identical.

Thus, a global group coefficient that is meant to account for overall base rate differences between groups can lead to large local effects, especially in the vicinity of the decision threshold, due to the non-linear shape of the sigmoid function. In the example, even a moderate difference of 0.05 closer to the margins corresponds to a large difference of 0.18 near the threshold, which can lead to a large disparate impact.

Figure 2: Predictions for aware and unaware logistic regression models on the ACS Income NY dataset. The aware model uses education and sex as input variables. The unaware model only considers education, measured in years. Colored vertical lines correspond to the 50% cut-off. Note how the aware logistic regression model requires much higher education values for women (yellow/red) than for men (blue) to be selected. This phenomenon is not observed in the unaware model.

This effect can be further illustrated with an example based on real data, namely the US Census data from New York, obtained from the ACS Income dataset from the `folktables` package [18] (see Section 5.1). In this case, the target variable is whether a person has an annual income of at least 50k. For illustration purposes, we restrict the logistic regression model to include only two variables: the most predictive attribute (education, in number of years) and the protected binary attribute (sex). Two logistic regression models using default hyperparameters are trained: one *aware* model, including education and sex, and one *unaware* model that uses education as the only input variable. The results are depicted in Figure 2: The aware model “pushes” the predictions for men and women apart, meaning that men need an education score of 20 (equivalent to an associate’s degree), whereas women need an education score of 22 (equivalent to a Master’s degree) to obtain a positive classification. Income for men is over-predicted around the threshold (the blue line being above the grey dashed base rate line), whereas for women it is under-predicted (the yellow line being below the grey dashed base rate line). Conversely, in the case of the unaware model, which does not include sex as an input variable, the blue line on the left and the orange line on the right are necessarily the same. In this case, men are predicted correctly at the threshold while women are slightly over-predicted (the yellow line being above the grey dashed base rate line). Overall, this results in a similar accuracy for the unaware model (69.9%), compared to the aware model (70.0%), while significantly reducing the disparate impact (more details can be found in Appendix A.3).⁶

Before empirically investigating larger datasets, we take a step back and theoretically analyse the effect as an instance of model multiplicity—the phenomenon that multiple models can have similar accuracy while differing in other properties, such as fairness.

4 Less Discriminatory Algorithms through Unawareness

In this section, we show that large differences between models with similar accuracy can be explained theoretically and that datapoints with predictions close to the decision threshold are particularly important for this. We provide the first tight upper bounds on model multiplicity and, based on that, derive bounds on the difference in disparate impact. We also provide a lower bound specifically for logistic regression classifiers.

4.1 General upper bounds on model multiplicity

We begin by establishing general results on model multiplicity and then explore their implications for disparate impact and unaware models that do not use the protected attribute. Let P denote the empirical distribution over X, Y , describing the available data; based on this we define the conditional $p(x) : x \mapsto P(Y = 1 | X = x)$ and marginal measure $\mu(U) : 2^{\mathcal{X}} \rightarrow [0, 1], U \mapsto \int_U P(x)dx$. Furthermore, let $B : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be a Bayes-optimal classifier (with $B(x) = 0$ for $p(x) < 0.5$ and $B(x) = 1$ for $p(x) > 0.5$). Now in line

⁶While the single feature case is an unrealistic illustration, the fact that the accuracy is not much lower than when using all features indicates that the feature drives most of the prediction. This already suggests that similar results occur in full datasets; we turn to this in Section 5.

with the closest previous work [7], we define L as the 0-1-loss

$$L(y_1, y_2) := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y_1 = y_2 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

We define the accuracy of a model F as

$$\text{Acc}(F) := 1 - \mathbb{E}_P[L(F(X), Y)] \quad (11)$$

and the disagreement between two models F, G as

$$d(F, G) := \mu(\{x \in X : F(x) \neq G(x)\}). \quad (12)$$

For $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{X}} := 2^{\mathcal{X}}$ the set of binary classifiers on \mathcal{X} , let

$$R_{\epsilon}(F) := \{G \in \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{X}} : \text{Acc}(G) \geq \text{Acc}(F) - \epsilon\} \quad (13)$$

be the ϵ -Rashomon set of F . For $\lambda \in [0, 0.5]$, let

$$U(\lambda) := \{x \in \mathcal{X} : |p(x) - 0.5| = \lambda\} \quad \text{and} \quad m(\lambda) := \mu(U(\lambda)) \quad (14)$$

measure how much each distance from 0.5 occurs, which is non-zero only on the set of occurring distances $\Lambda := \{|p(x) - 0.5| : x \in \mathcal{X}\}$. Then we define new quantities

$$e(\lambda) := \sum_{\lambda' < \lambda} 2\lambda' \cdot m(\lambda') \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_{\epsilon} := \arg \max_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \{\lambda : e(\lambda) \leq \epsilon\}, \quad (15)$$

which are illustrated in Figure 7 in Appendix B. Intuitively, $e(\lambda)$ is the additional error if for all points with label ratios closer to 50% than λ , the suboptimal classification is taken, and λ_{ϵ} is the largest λ such that this error does not exceed ϵ . With these definitions at hand, we can prove a tight upper bound on model multiplicity, which is proved through a lemma on randomised classifiers. The dependence of our tight bound on λ_{ϵ} and $e(\lambda_{\epsilon})$ demonstrates how important input space regions with a near-50% label ratio are for model multiplicity.

PROPOSITION 2 (UPPER BOUND ON MULTIPLICITY).

$$\max_{F \in R_{\epsilon}(B)} d(F, B) \leq \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_{\epsilon})}{2\lambda_{\epsilon}} + \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_{\epsilon}} m(\lambda). \quad (16)$$

This bound is the tightest possible bound with only access to the cumulative distribution of $p(x)$.

LEMMA 1. The bound (16) can be achieved in any setting for every ϵ by a randomised classifier defined as

$$F_{\epsilon}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - B(x) & \text{for } |p(x) - 0.5| < \lambda_{\epsilon} \\ 1 - B(x) \text{ with probability } \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_{\epsilon})}{2\lambda_{\epsilon} \cdot m(\lambda_{\epsilon})} & \text{for } |p(x) - 0.5| = \lambda_{\epsilon} \\ B(x) & \text{for } |p(x) - 0.5| > \lambda_{\epsilon}. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

This means the maximum is achieved if the predictions with $p(x)$ closest to 0.5 are flipped until the accuracy decreases by ϵ . All proofs, as well as illustrations of these results and the quantity $e(\lambda)$ can be found in Appendix B.

We now relate this bound to a **previous result**: Black et al. [7] provide a formal upper bound on how much a model can disagree with another model when the difference in accuracy is controlled. We can also recover their result in the proof of their Theorem A.2, that

$$d(F, B) \leq \frac{\text{Acc}(B) - \text{Acc}(F)}{2c} \quad (18)$$

under the assumption⁷

$$|p(x) - 0.5| \geq c > 0 \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}. \quad (19)$$

COROLLARY 1. Under assumption (19),

$$\max_{F \in R_{\epsilon}(B)} d(F, B) \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2c}. \quad (20)$$

While the above bounds involved an optimal classifier, we can also give bounds for **two non-optimal models**.

PROPOSITION 3 (MULTIPLICITY BOUND FOR NON-OPTIMAL MODELS).

We can bound the disagreement between two classifiers $F \in R_{\epsilon}(B)$ and $G \in R_{\delta}(B)$ via

$$d(F, G) \leq \max_{H \in R_{\epsilon+\delta}(B)} d(H, B). \quad (21)$$

That is, the maximum possible disagreement between F and G is no greater than the largest disagreement that any model H within accuracy drop $\epsilon + \delta$ could have with B itself. We now connect this bound to **disparate impact**.

PROPOSITION 4 (UPPER BOUND ON DISPARATE IMPACT). For two classifiers F and G , the difference in their disparate impact can be bounded based on their disagreement and the size of the smaller group:

$$|\text{DI}(F) - \text{DI}(G)| \leq \frac{d(F, G)}{\min_{* \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}} P(X \in *)}. \quad (22)$$

That is, the potential difference in disparate impact between two models increases with their disagreement, and it is inversely proportional to the size of the smallest protected group. We can also specify a bound for the context of **Fairness through Unawareness**. The above bound is not tight when an unaware model is involved, unless for all $\bigcup_{\lambda < \lambda_{\epsilon}} U(\lambda)$, the two groups are separable in $U(\lambda)$ by the protected attribute alone. If this is not the case, then the unaware model will give the same decision for some $x_1, x_2 \in \bigcup_{\lambda < \lambda_{\epsilon}} U(\lambda)$ from different groups; so flipping the decisions on both x_1 and x_2 , which is necessary for equality in (16), will not lead to a proportional rise in DI, i.e., there is no equality in (22). However, we can show that half the bound is achievable for some ϵ :

PROPOSITION 5 (ACHIEVABLE DI FOR UNAWARE MODELS). Fix P , an unaware model F , and some $\epsilon > 0$. Then there is a model $G \in R_{\epsilon}(F)$ with

$$|\text{DI}(F) - \text{DI}(G)| \geq \frac{1}{2 \cdot \max_{* \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}} P(X \in *)} \max_{H \in R_{\epsilon+\delta}(B)} d(H, B). \quad (23)$$

4.2 A lower bound for logistic regression

We now turn to the specific case of LR models. The following result provides a lower bound on the reducible DI for a fixed change in accuracy. This bound depends on the coefficient of the protected attribute and the calibration plots for both groups, including bin sizes. Similar to the results presented above, it crucially depends on changes in classification decisions near the decision threshold, highlighting the importance of data points near the decision threshold.

⁷Black et al. assume $|p(x) - 0.5| > c$ but it is not necessary to assume that the inequality is strict.

PROPOSITION 6 (LOWER BOUND ON DI FOR LR). Let $F : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be an aware classifier based on an LR model f with coefficient $c_G < 0$ for the PA, i.e., the disadvantaged group gets a pre-sigmoid penalty of c_G . Further, let

$$Q(c_G) := \{x \in \mathcal{B} : f(x) \in [\sigma(c_G), 0.5]\} \quad (24)$$

denote the set of points that are in Group b and get predictions between $\sigma(c_G)$ and 0.5 by f . Then the corresponding unaware classifier F' based on setting $c_{PA} \leftarrow 0$ in F has accuracy bounded by

$$|\text{Acc}(F) - \text{Acc}(F')| \leq 2\sigma(-c_G) \cdot P(X \in Q(c_G)) \quad (25)$$

and disparate impact given by

$$\text{DI}(F') = \text{DI}(F) - P(X \in Q(c_G))/P(X \in \mathcal{B}) \quad (26)$$

if group b is still disadvantaged in F' (i.e. $\text{DI}(F) \geq P(X \in Q(c_G))/P(X \in \mathcal{B})$), and otherwise

$$|\text{DI}(F) - \text{DI}(F')| \leq P(X \in Q(c_G))/P(X \in \mathcal{B}). \quad (27)$$

The focus on one specific unaware model provides a loose but already interesting lower bound on the possible reduction of DI: As a quantitative example, consider the ACS Income dataset discussed in the following section. In this setting, a logistic regression model assigns a coefficient of -0.86 for the protected attribute sex. We observe that the proportion of women is $P(X \in \mathcal{B}) = 0.48$ and $P(X \in Q(c_G)) = 6.9\%$ is the set of women whose predicted probabilities fall within the range $[0.5, 0.70)$, corresponding to the sigmoid of 0.86, i.e., $\sigma(0.86) = 0.70$. If we were to flip decisions in this region, the accuracy would change by at most 0.7 percentage points either down or up, while the disparate impact would decrease by at least 14.5 percentage points.⁸

Note that this result only represents one possible model within the $(2\sigma(-c_G) \cdot P(X \in Q(c_G)))$ -Rashomon set, and therefore serves as a lower bound on the achievable DI reduction. It is unlikely to be optimal since it optimises the other coefficients ‘under the assumption’ that c_G will be used; it also only modifies the predictions for women, leaving the men’s unchanged. In summary, we have provided general upper bounds on disparate impact reduction within some ϵ -Rashomon set that are achievable for unconstrained model classes and we have a naïve lower bound for logistic regression. In the next section, we empirically investigate how unaware and aware models compare on real datasets.

5 Empirical findings

After the theoretical results above, we now empirically analyse the effect of Fairness through Unawareness (FtU) on Disparate Impact (DI) and Accuracy. We consider three datasets, with different model classes and protected attributes. All code, also for Section 3.2 above, is available at <https://github.com/ben-hoeltgen/ftu-mm/>.

5.1 Setup

1. Models: We analyse the behaviour of two model classes, logistic regression (LR) and gradient-boosted decision trees (GBM), using the popular `scikit-learn` package (more details in Appendix A.2).

⁸With a base accuracy of 77.4% and a DI of 0.052, this translates to a relative accuracy change of 0.009 vs a relative reduction in DI of 0.64—see Figure 3.

2. Data: We perform experiments on three datasets: The ACS Income and ACS Employment datasets from the `folktables` package [18] from the US Census and the active labour market policy (ALMP) evaluation dataset from Switzerland [29]. Table 3 in Appendix A.1 contains a summary of the data. In ACS Income and ACS Employment, the target variables are whether a person’s income is above 50k and whether they are employed, respectively. We consider two binary protected attributes: sex (male/female) and race (white/black). Note that the US Census asks for sex rather than gender, which is reflected in the derived dataset. Race is self-indicated in the census, and we restrict to the white/black categories.⁹ In the ALMP dataset, our target variable is whether a person will be employed for at least 6 months within the next two years. We consider two binary protected attributes: gender (male/female) and citizenship (Swiss/foreign). In line with previous literature [46], we exclude caseworker information and restrict data to German-speaking cantons.

5.2 Results

Figure 3: Relative reduction in Accuracy vs in Disparate Impact (DI) across three datasets, with two model classes (LR: logistic regression and GBM: gradient boosted trees) and two protected attributes (PAs) each. Each dot corresponds to the difference in Accuracy and DI between the aware and the corresponding unaware model trained on the same random train/test split. Note how the unaware model achieves a reduction in accuracy which is always below 1% and sometimes it even increases, while yielding a reduction in DI that is much more substantial (between 15 – 80%).

⁹We want to emphasise that race categories are an over-simplification of the complex notion of racialization. Their use should always be contextualised and avoided where possible [19].

The main results, shown in Figure 3, indicate that Accuracy remains similar between aware and unaware models (*i.e.*, models that exclude the protected attribute), while DI is often significantly reduced in the unaware models, yielding fairer models with similar levels of accuracy.¹⁰ The results on the ALMP dataset show general multiplicity, whereas the results on the ACS datasets exhibit less multiplicity. This is not surprising, given that the number of data points is much larger in the ACS datasets than in the ALMP dataset (Table 3). The fact that the observed results hold on such large datasets suggests that the effect does not simply disappear with more data.

When considering race as the protected attribute in the ACS datasets, the reduction in disparate impact is generally smaller than with sex, but reaches around 20% across all settings at virtually no loss in accuracy. For settings where sex is the protected attribute, there is an interesting difference in the results on the ACS Income vs the ACS Employment datasets. On ACS Income, the largest reduction in DI ($\approx 80\%$) is obtained with the unaware LR model (consistent with, but slightly exceeding, the lower bound of Section 3.2, see footnote 8). In contrast, on ACS Employment, the largest reduction of DI (also $\approx 80\%$) corresponds to the unaware GBM. This result can be explained by two effects that are observable in Figure 4. First, aware LR can lead to particularly high disparate impact, as discussed in Section 3.2. This effect is particularly pronounced when sex is the protected attribute. For instance, in the case of the ACS Income dataset, the LR model leads to a disparate impact that far exceeds the base rate difference in the data (indicated by the red line). Second, in the ACS Employment dataset, the LR model with sex as the protected attribute actually results in higher positive classification rates for women than for men, suggesting that women may have stronger predictive features for employment than men. As a result, the change in disparity between men and women is more noticeable with LR than with GBM (see Figure 4), even though the absolute DI values change less (see Figure 3). This difference between ACS Employment and ACS Income can be attributed to the lower base rate differences in the former (see Table 3).

6 Discussion: Real-world use case

We have shown that including protected attributes like sex or gender in models can lead to substantially less equitable classifications, often without meaningful gains in accuracy—and sometimes without improving accuracy at all. However, what ultimately matters is not just how models classify individuals, but the real-world impact that these systems have when used to guide decisions. In other words, what matters are the *policies* that these models inform [28]. As others have pointed out, “[i]t is policies and their effects that are just or unjust; ‘fair’ predictors can both support unjust policies and undermine just policy” [46, p. 1984]. Machine learning models are increasingly used in resource allocation, where limited goods or opportunities—like counselling or training programs—are distributed based on risk predictions, often through threshold-based

¹⁰This result is consistent with previous analysis on the German unemployment data, where it was observed that “in- or excluding protected attributes has little effect on overall performance” [27]. However, this observation is not further discussed there.

Figure 4: Disparate impact for the aware and unaware models in different settings. The red lines indicate the difference in base rates in the data. Note how the unaware models achieve lower disparate impact than the aware models.

policies.¹¹ An important question is whether predictions are even helpful in such contexts [35, 36, 44]. Furthermore, there is the concern that predicting risk irrespective of treatment may not suffice since this risk does not necessarily correlate with treatment effectiveness [43, 46]. With these caveats, we now turn to examine the impact of Fairness through Unawareness in a real-world application that has attracted considerable attention in Europe in recent years: the statistical profiling of job seekers, which is increasingly used in labour market programs across the world to support decisions on how to allocate resources such as job training opportunities [17]. These systems aim to predict an individual’s risk of long-term unemployment such that costly services can be targeted more efficiently, ideally to those for whom the intervention will have the greatest positive impact. Different models use different predictors. For example, gender has been explicitly included in profiling models used in Australia [30] and Austria [25].

A recent example is the Austrian AMS algorithm, which uses an undisclosed stratification procedure [22] that is approximated by a published logistic regression model [25], and includes gender as a feature. The AMS algorithm has sparked significant legal and political controversy, leading to multiple revisions and delays in its deployment. As a result, it has not yet been implemented in practice. Critics argue that the model creates a false impression of objectivity and has been specifically accused of reinforcing gender discrimination [1]. The Austrian system stands out by targeting individuals of medium risk: the model categorizes job seekers into three groups—low (A), medium (B) and high (C) risk of long-term unemployment—but only those in the medium-risk group (B) are offered access to the costly job training programs. There are various issues with this approach, most notably its reliance on observational data to make causal claims [43, 46], such as the assumption that individuals at medium risk benefit the most from the intervention. In line with the broader theme of this paper, we highlight another common but flawed assumption: that using more attributes necessarily leads to more objective (and hence fairer) decisions. One major criticism of the AMS algorithm has been its discriminatory impact,

¹¹While our analyses have focused on the 50% threshold, we show below that the underlying insights apply more broadly.

especially with regard to gender. The model assigned a negative coefficient of -0.14 to women and applied an additional penalty for care obligations, a variable that is only present for women. As a result, 5% of women were placed in the high-risk group C—deemed ineligible for job training—when compared to only 3% of men [25]. Defenders of the system argued that its predictions simply reflect actual labour market conditions, stating it follows “*the real chances on the labour market as far as possible*” (as cited in Allhutter et al. [1]).

Model	Mode	Male	Female	$\Delta \downarrow$	AUROC \uparrow
LR	Aware	1.6% \pm 0.1%	2.2% \pm 0.2%	0.7% \pm 0.3%	0.680 \pm 0.002
	Unaware	1.7% \pm 0.1%	2.0% \pm 0.2%	0.2% \pm 0.2%	0.680 \pm 0.002
GBM	Aware	3.9% \pm 0.3%	8.3% \pm 0.4%	4.4% \pm 0.4%	0.700 \pm 0.003
	Unaware	4.5% \pm 0.1%	6.1% \pm 0.2%	1.6% \pm 0.2%	0.697 \pm 0.003

Table 2: Group C sizes for both the aware and unaware LR and GBM models on the original ALMP dataset (means and STDs over 10 random splits). The Δ column reflects the difference between men and women. Note how the unaware models yield more equitable results with negligible loss in accuracy. Best results indicated in bold font.

However, as shown in previous sections, there is no direct or reliable link between observed label rates (or supposed ‘real chances’) and the disparities in outcomes produced by model-based decisions. In the following analysis, we reconstruct the AMS setting as faithfully as possible (given the lack of access to the original data) and explore the effects of excluding gender on both accuracy and disparate impact. Lacking the original data, we base our analysis on the active labour market policy (ALMP) dataset from Switzerland [29], focusing on the German-speaking cantons. Although the features in this dataset differ somewhat from those used in the AMS model, we aim to approximate the setting, not replicate it exactly. We adopt the same prediction target used by the AMS algorithm to determine assignment to group C, namely, whether an individual is employed for at least 6 out of the next 24 months.¹² We train both LR and GBM models and present the results in Table 2. In our analysis, we focus on two main outcomes: (1) the per-gender proportion of individuals assigned to group C (those considered too high-risk to receive job training), and the difference between genders; and (2) the AUROC of the models, given that the decision criterion is the 25% threshold. As reflected in Table 2, while omitting gender has little impact on AUROC, it leads to a more balanced assignment between genders, *i.e.*, the proportion of individuals deemed too risky is more equitable in the unaware model. Hence, even if there is no straightforward connection between AUROC and efficiency, these results suggest that Fairness through Unawareness can lead to more equitable but equally efficient policies in practice.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we have shown that unaware models, which omit a protected attribute, can significantly reduce disparate impact

¹²A second model with a slightly different target is used to determine assignment to group A.

across groups defined by that attribute while maintaining accuracy. Our theoretical and empirical analysis suggests that this effect is common, at least on tabular data. Our findings urge caution when using logistic regression, as it can produce unintended disparities. Note that our analyses do not suggest that LR or protected attributes should never be used (although there can be legal constraints), nor that FtU is sufficient for ensuring fair algorithmic decision-making. Indeed, we did not compare FtU to fairness interventions, such as threshold adjustments, precisely because our point is less about achieving SOTA results than about demonstrating the importance of more basic modelling choices (even though such a comparison may be of interest for the intervention perspective). In this sense, our results underscore the need for critical evaluation of algorithmic choices as part of the broader deployment pipeline of machine learning models [5]. More generally, our results challenge the notion of a strict fairness-accuracy trade-off, which has been theoretically suggested based on true distributions and Bayes-optimal predictors [14, 32]. We argue that the relevance of such theoretical claims to real-world applications should be scrutinised, given the potential dangers of uncritically applying idealised assumptions to real-world problems with consequential impact on people’s lives [26].

Ethical considerations

A potential adverse effect of this work is that it could induce model designers to exclude protected attributes by default, even in cases where the benefits may outweigh the harms, as suggested to be the case for some health settings [14]. However, our work does not warrant such a conclusion and we generally suggest investigating both unaware and aware models where possible. Another unwarranted inference would be to claim that unawareness is enough for ensuring fairness or equality — this conclusion is also not supported by our work; we merely show that it can be a useful means toward this end.

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A More details on experimental setups

All code is available at <https://github.com/ben-hoeltgen/ftu-mm/>.

A.1 Datasets

The Swiss ALMP dataset features include education, demographics (gender, marital status, age), nationality, region, three related to employment history, two macroeconomic indicators, eight features on previous job characteristics, and ten features on completed job training programs. More information can be found on the dataset website [29]. The features used in the ACS datasets are listed in Table 5. For more details, we refer to the original publication [18].

A.2 Models

We use default settings LogisticRegression in scikit-learn but tune GradientBoostingClassifier for higher accuracy. The parameters are `n_estimators=500`, `max_depth=10`, `max_leaf_nodes=50`, `min_samples_leaf=500`, very similar to the optimal parameters on the ACS datasets according to previous work ([16], personal communication). We use the same settings for the ALMP experiments. The accuracies for the default aware models are reported in Table 4 for comparability.

Dataset	# Features	PA	PA Values	Group Size	DBR	# Datapoints
ACS Income	9/10	Sex	male/female	52.1%	0.15	1,664,500
		Race	white/black	89.8%	0.14	1,445,699
ACS Employment	15/16	Sex	male/female	49.0%	0.06	3,236,107
		Race	white/black	88.9%	0.06	2,796,670
ALMP	28/29	Gender	male/female	56.2%	0.04	69,372
		Citizenship	Swiss/foreign	64.3%	0.17	69,372

Table 3: Datasets summary. The number of features differs by one (protected attribute) between aware and unaware models. The 'Group Size' column indicates the proportion of data points belonging to the advantaged group, and the 'DBR' column contains the Disparate Benefit Ratio, which is the ratio of favourable outcomes received by the disadvantaged group compared to the advantaged group, indicating the degree of inequality in model predictions across protected groups. When this ratio is much smaller than 1, it indicates disparate treatment.

Model	ACS Inc (sex)	ACS Inc (race)	ACS Empl (sex)	ACS Empl (race)	ALMP
LR	77.4% ± 0.1%	77.1% ± 0.0%	77.9% ± 0.0%	78.1% ± 0.1%	65.0% ± 0.4%
GBM	82.1% ± 0.1%	81.8% ± 0.1%	83.2% ± 0.1%	83.2% ± 0.0%	66.2% ± 0.3%

Table 4: Accuracies per setting for the aware model with standard deviations. The accuracies of aware models on ACS datasets differ between the sex and the race setting since we only use a subset of the data in the latter, restricting to 'white' and 'black'.

ACS Employment	ACS Income
SCHL: Education	SCHL: Education
MAR: Marital status	MAR: Marital status
AGEP: Age	AGEP: Age
RAC1P: Race	RAC1P: Race
RELP: Relationship	RELP: Relationship
SEX: Sex	SEX: Sex
DEYE: Vision difficulty	
ANC: Ancestry	
DREM: Cognitive difficulty	
MIG: Move in last year	
CIT: Citizenship	
DIS: Disability	
DEAR: Hearing difficulty	
MIL: Military service	
NATIVITY: Born in US	
ESP: Employment status of parents	
	OCCP: Occupation
	WKHP: Work hours per week
	COW: Class of worker
	POBP: Place of birth

Table 5: Features used in ACS Employment and Income.

A.3 Single feature experiment

Here, we give more details on the single feature experiments described in Section 3.2. Classification rates for the aware model are at 0.477 (men) and 0.212 (women). Histograms of the X value distribution (Figure 5) show that among women, there is a higher

fraction of highly educated individuals, especially with a Master's degree. This results in a higher classification rate for women (0.449) compared to men (0.389) in the unaware model, still significantly reducing the (absolute) disparate impact. We also show model predictions for aware and unaware GBM models (Figure 6). Here, the threshold for the unaware model is the same as for LR, whereas the aware model has a higher threshold for men (21) compared with the aware LR model (same as the threshold of the unaware models). The accuracy of the aware GBM model is slightly higher, at 70.3%, and the classification rates are 0.389 (men) and 0.212 (women). This still means a much higher disparate impact than for the unaware model.

Figure 5: Histogram of the distribution of X values along the education dimension for men (blue) and women (orange/red). vertical lines denote the thresholds induced by the aware (left) and unaware (right) model.

Figure 6: Predictions for aware and unaware GBM models on ACS Income NY when only using education as an input. Vertical colors indicate the 50% cutoff, highlighting that the aware GBM model requires much higher education for women than for men.

B Proofs

B.1 Results in Section 3

PROPOSITION 1 (RELATION BETWEEN BASE RATES AND DISPARATE IMPACT).

Assume f is calibrated as in (4), satisfying $\forall v \in [0, 0.5] : P_{\mathcal{B}}(v) \geq P_{\mathcal{A}}(v)$ and $\forall v \in [0.5, 1] : P_{\mathcal{A}}(v) \geq P_{\mathcal{B}}(v)$. Then for F defined as in (1), $DI(F) \geq DBR$.

PROOF.

$$DI(F) = P_{\mathcal{A}}(V_a \geq 0.5) - P_{\mathcal{B}}(V_b \geq 0.5) \quad (28)$$

$$= \int_{[0.5, 1]} P_{\mathcal{A}}(v) - P_{\mathcal{B}}(v) \, dv \quad (29)$$

$$\geq \int_F (P_{\mathcal{A}}(v) - P_{\mathcal{B}}(v)) \cdot v \, dv \quad (30)$$

$$\geq \int_{[0.5, 1]} (P_{\mathcal{A}}(v) - P_{\mathcal{B}}(v)) \cdot v \, dv + \int_{[0, 0.5]} (P_{\mathcal{A}}(v) - P_{\mathcal{B}}(v)) \cdot v \, dv \quad (31)$$

$$= \int_{[0, 0.5]} P_{\mathcal{A}}(v) \cdot v \, dv + \int_{[0.5, 1]} P_{\mathcal{A}}(v) \cdot v \, dv - \left(\int_{[0, 0.5]} P_{\mathcal{B}}(v) \cdot v \, dv + \int_{[0.5, 1]} P_{\mathcal{B}}(v) \cdot v \, dv \right) \quad (32)$$

$$= \mathbb{E}_{P_{\mathcal{A}}}[V_a] - \mathbb{E}_{P_{\mathcal{B}}}[V_b] = DBR \quad (33)$$

□

As can be seen from the proof, the assumptions in Proposition 1 can be relaxed to, respectively,

$$\int_{[0.5, 1]} P_{\mathcal{A}}(v) \cdot (1 - v) \, dv \geq \int_{[0.5, 1]} P_{\mathcal{B}}(v) \cdot (1 - v) \, dv, \quad (34)$$

and

$$\int_{[0, 0.5]} P_{\mathcal{B}}(v) \cdot v \, dv \geq \int_{[0, 0.5]} P_{\mathcal{A}}(v) \cdot v \, dv. \quad (35)$$

The left hand side of (35) is equivalent to $\mathbb{E}_{P_{\mathcal{B}}}[V_b | V_b < 0.5] \cdot P(\{V_b < 0.5\})$, i.e. the mean of the predictions below the decision threshold times the probability mass below the threshold.

Figure 7: Illustration of $e(\lambda)$ in the case of the earlier example: $e(\lambda)$ is the additional error if for all predictions closer to 50% than λ , the suboptimal classification is taken. An illustration for $\lambda = 0.15$ is given.

Figure 8: Illustration of λ_ϵ and $e(\lambda_\epsilon)$: λ_ϵ is the highest divergence from 0.5 s.t. switching all predictions closer than λ_ϵ to 50% increases the error rate by less than ϵ .

B.2 Results in Section 4

We start with the lemma on randomised classifiers.

LEMMA 1.

The bound (45) can be achieved in any setting for every ϵ by a randomised classifier defined as

$$F_\epsilon(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - B(x) & \text{for } |p(x) - 0.5| < \lambda_\epsilon \\ 1 - B(x) \text{ with prob } \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot m(\lambda_\epsilon)} & \text{for } |p(x) - 0.5| = \lambda_\epsilon \\ B(x) & \text{for } |p(x) - 0.5| > \lambda_\epsilon. \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

PROOF.

Take some \mathcal{X} and P and ϵ . Then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Acc}(F_\epsilon) &= \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \cdot (0.5 - \lambda) + \sum_{\lambda > \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \cdot (0.5 + \lambda) \\ &+ \left(m(\lambda_\epsilon) \cdot \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot m(\lambda_\epsilon)} \cdot (0.5 - \lambda_\epsilon) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ m(\lambda_\epsilon) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot m(\lambda_\epsilon)} \right) \cdot (0.5 + \lambda_\epsilon) \\ &= \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \cdot (0.5 + \lambda - 2\lambda) + \sum_{\lambda > \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \cdot (0.5 + \lambda) \\ &+ m(\lambda_\epsilon) \cdot \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot m(\lambda_\epsilon)} \cdot (0.5 + \lambda_\epsilon - 2\lambda_\epsilon) \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ m(\lambda_\epsilon) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot m(\lambda_\epsilon)} \right) \cdot (0.5 + \lambda_\epsilon) \\ &= \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \cdot (0.5 + \lambda) + \sum_{\lambda > \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \cdot (0.5 + \lambda) \\ &- \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \cdot 2\lambda + m(\lambda_\epsilon) \cdot (0.5 + \lambda_\epsilon) \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &- m(\lambda_\epsilon) \cdot \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot m(\lambda_\epsilon)} \cdot 2\lambda_\epsilon \\ &= \sum_{\lambda \in \Lambda} m(\lambda) \cdot (0.5 + \lambda) - e(\lambda_\epsilon) - m(\lambda_\epsilon) \cdot \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot m(\lambda_\epsilon)} \cdot 2\lambda_\epsilon \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

$$= \text{Acc}(B) - \epsilon \quad (41)$$

and

$$d(F_\epsilon, B) = \mu(\{x \in \mathcal{X} : F(x) \neq B(x)\}) \quad (42)$$

$$= \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) + \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot m(\lambda_\epsilon)} \cdot m(\lambda_\epsilon) \quad (43)$$

$$= \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon} + \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda). \quad (44)$$

□

This lemma helps to prove our new bound on model multiplicity.

PROPOSITION 2 (UPPER BOUND ON MULTIPLICITY).

$$\max_{F \in \mathcal{R}_\epsilon(B)} d(F, B) \leq \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon} + \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \quad (45)$$

This bound is the lowest possible bound with only access to the cumulative distribution of $p(x)$.

PROOF.

We now show that no randomised classifier represented as F :

$\mathcal{X} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $\text{Acc}(F)\lambda_\epsilon \text{Acc}(B) - \epsilon$ can disagree more with B on expectation than F_ϵ . Then *a fortiori*, there can be no deterministic classifier that breaks the bound. Now for any randomised classifier F with $d(F, B) > d(F_\epsilon, B)$, we show $\text{Acc}(F) < \text{Acc}(F_\epsilon)$. Let the average prediction on $U(\lambda)$ be given by

$$f(\lambda) := \frac{1}{m(\lambda)} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} \mu(\{x\}) |F(x) - 0.5|. \quad (46)$$

By construction of F_ϵ ,

$$\forall \lambda < \lambda_\epsilon : \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} |B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)| \geq |B(x) - F(x)| \quad (47)$$

and

$$\forall \lambda > \lambda_\epsilon : \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} |B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)| \leq |B(x) - F(x)| \quad (48)$$

Then $d(F, B) > d(F_\epsilon, B)$ implies that

$$0 \leq \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} (|B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)| - |B(x) - F(x)|) \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \quad (49)$$

$$< \sum_{\lambda \geq \lambda_\epsilon} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} (|B(x) - F(x)| - |B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)|) \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \quad (50)$$

But since $\forall \lambda \in \Lambda, x \in U(\lambda)$ and any randomised classifier G ,

$$\mathbb{E}_P[L(G(X), Y)|X = x] = \mathbb{E}_P[L(B(X), Y)|X = x] + |B(x) - G(x)| \cdot 2\lambda \quad (51)$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Acc}(F_\epsilon) - \text{Acc}(F) &= \text{Acc}(B) - \sum_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} |B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)| \cdot 2\lambda \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \\ &- \text{Acc}(B) + \sum_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} |B(x) - F(x)| \cdot 2\lambda \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} (|B(x) - F(x)| - |B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)|) \cdot 2\lambda \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \quad (53) \\ &= \sum_{\lambda \geq \lambda_\epsilon} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} (|B(x) - F(x)| - |B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)|) \cdot 2\lambda \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \\ &- \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} (|B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)| - |B(x) - F(x)|) \cdot 2\lambda \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \sum_{\lambda \geq \lambda_\epsilon} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} (|B(x) - F(x)| - |B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)|) \cdot 2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \\ &- \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} (|B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)| - |B(x) - F(x)|) \cdot 2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &> 0. \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

We now show that the bound is tight in the sense that for any cumulative distribution (defined by Λ and m), we can i) for each ϵ find a $\mathcal{X}, P(X)$ and ii) for each $\mathcal{X}, P(X)$ find an $\epsilon > 0$ so that the bound is achievable.

i) Take some Λ , m and ϵ . Then let \mathcal{X} be such that there is $x_0 \in U(\lambda_\epsilon)$ with $\mu(\{x_0\}) = \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon}$ and let

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - B(x) & \text{for } |p(x) - 0.5| < \lambda_\epsilon \\ 1 - B(x) & \text{for } x = x_0 \\ B(x) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (57)$$

Then, similar to F_ϵ in the Lemma,

$$\text{Acc}(B) - \text{Acc}(F_\epsilon) = \sum_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \sum_{x \in U(\lambda)} |B(x) - F_\epsilon(x)| \cdot 2\lambda \cdot \mu(\{x\}) \quad (58)$$

$$= 2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot \mu(\{x_0\}) + \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} 2\lambda \cdot m(\lambda) \quad (59)$$

$$= 2\lambda_\epsilon \cdot \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon} + e(\lambda_\epsilon) \quad (60)$$

$$= \epsilon \quad (61)$$

and

$$d(F, B) = \mu(\{x \in \mathcal{X} : F(x) \neq B(x)\}) \quad (62)$$

$$= \mu(\{x\}) + \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \quad (63)$$

$$= \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda_\epsilon} + \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda). \quad (64)$$

□

	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4
$B(x)$	0	0	1	1
$F_1(x)$	0	0	0	1
$F_2(x)$	0	1	0	1
$F_3(x)$	1	1	1	1
$F_4(x)$	1	1	0	1

Figure 9: Illustration of Proposition 2. The table gives the classifiers derived from the calibrated predictors in Table 1 plus an additional classifier F_4 . We show that our bound refines the bound (18) from [7], and is applicable under on fewer assumptions.

COROLLARY 1.

Under assumption (19),

$$\max_{F \in R_\epsilon(B)} d(F, B) \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2c}. \quad (65)$$

PROOF.

From (19), we get $\forall \lambda \in \Lambda : \lambda \geq c$ and hence

$$\frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2\lambda} + \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \leq \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2c} + \sum_{\lambda < \lambda_\epsilon} m(\lambda) \frac{2\lambda}{2c} \quad (66)$$

$$= \frac{\epsilon - e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2c} + \frac{e(\lambda_\epsilon)}{2c} \quad (67)$$

$$= \frac{\epsilon}{2c} \quad (68)$$

and thus the Proposition entails

$$\max_{F \in R_\epsilon(B)} d(F, B) \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2c}. \quad (69)$$

□

PROPOSITION 3 (MULTIPLICITY BOUND FOR NON-OPTIMAL MODELS).

We can bound the disagreement between two classifiers $F \in R_\epsilon(B)$ and $G \in R_\delta(B)$ via

$$d(F, G) \leq \max_{H \in R_{\epsilon+\delta}(B)} d(H, B). \quad (70)$$

PROOF.

Fix F and G and let $U := \{x \in \mathcal{X} : F(x) \neq G(x)\}$. Now define a classifier H via

$$H(x) := \begin{cases} 1 - B(x) & \text{for } x \in U \\ B(x) & \text{for } x \notin U. \end{cases} \quad (71)$$

Then $d(B, H) = \mu(U) = d(F, G) \leq d(F, B) + d(G, B) \leq \epsilon + \delta$ and thus $H \in R_{\epsilon+\delta}(B)$. The result follows. □

PROPOSITION 4 (UPPER BOUND ON DISPARATE IMPACT).

For two classifiers F and G , the difference in their disparate impact can be bounded based on their disagreement and the size of the smaller group:

$$|\text{DI}(F) - \text{DI}(G)| \leq \frac{d(F, G)}{\min_{* \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}} P(X \in *)}. \quad (72)$$

PROOF.

$$|\text{DI}(F) - \text{DI}(G)| = |P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}) - P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B}) - P(G(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}) + P(G(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B})| \quad (73)$$

$$= |P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}) - P(G(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}) + P(G(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B}) - P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B})| \quad (74)$$

$$\leq P(F(X) \neq G(X) | X \in \mathcal{A}) + P(F(X) \neq G(X) | X \in \mathcal{B}) \quad (75)$$

$$\leq d(F, G) / \min_{* \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}} P(X \in *) \quad (76)$$

since

$$d(F, G) = P(F(X) \neq G(X)) \quad (77)$$

$$= P(F(X) \neq G(X) | X \in \mathcal{A}) \cdot P(X \in \mathcal{A}) + P(F(X) \neq G(X) | X \in \mathcal{B}) \cdot P(X \in \mathcal{B}) \quad (78)$$

$$\geq P(F(X) \neq G(X) | X \in \mathcal{A}) \cdot \min_{* \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}} P(X \in *)$$

$$+ P(F(X) \neq G(X) | X \in \mathcal{B}) \cdot \min_{* \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}} P(X \in *). \quad (79)$$

□

PROPOSITION 5 (ACHIEVABLE DI FOR UNAWARE MODELS).

Fix an H that achieves the maximum and let $U := \{x \in \mathcal{X} : H(x) \neq B(x)\}$. Then define two classifiers $G_{>}$ and $G_{<}$ via

$$|DI(F) - DI(G)| \geq \frac{1}{2 \cdot \max_{* \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}} P(X \in *)} \max_{H \in \mathcal{R}_{\epsilon+\delta}(B)} d(H, B). \quad (80)$$

PROOF.

Fix an H that achieves the maximum and let $U := \{x \in \mathcal{X} : H(x) \neq B(x)\}$. Then define two classifiers $G_{>}$ and $G_{<}$ via

$$G_{>}(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } x \in U \cap \mathcal{A} \text{ and } F(x) = 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } x \in U \cap \mathcal{B} \text{ and } F(x) = 1 \\ F(x) & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (81)$$

and

$$G_{<}(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } x \in U \cap \mathcal{B} \text{ and } F(x) = 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } x \in U \cap \mathcal{A} \text{ and } F(x) = 1 \\ F(x) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (82)$$

Then $\{x \in \mathcal{X} : H(x) \neq B(x)\} = U = \{x \in \mathcal{X} : F(x) \neq G_{<}(x)\} \cup \{x \in \mathcal{X} : F(x) \neq G_{>}(x)\}$ and hence

$$d(F, G_{\#}) \geq \frac{1}{2} d(H, B) \quad (83)$$

for one $\# \in \{<, >\}$. Furthermore, we get

$$|DI(F) - DI(G_{\#})| \geq \frac{d(F, G_{\#})}{\max_{* \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}\}} P(X \in *)} \quad (84)$$

by the same derivation as for (72) but with equality in (75) due to the construction of $G_{\#}$ and with ' \geq ' in (76) by switching min to max. \square

PROPOSITION 6 (LOWER BOUND ON DI FOR LR).

Let $F : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be an PA-aware classifier based on a LR model f with coefficient $c_G < 0$ for the PA, i.e. the disadvantaged group gets a pre-sigmoid penalty of c_G . Further, let

$$Q(c_G) := \{x \in \mathcal{B} : f(x) \in [\sigma(c_G), 0.5]\} \quad (85)$$

denote the set of points that get predictions between $\sigma(c_G)$ and 0.5 by f and are in Group b . Then the corresponding unaware classifier F' based on setting $c_{PA} \leftarrow 0$ in F has accuracy bounded by

$$|Acc(F) - Acc(F')| \leq 2\sigma(-c_G) \cdot P(X \in Q(c_G)) \quad (86)$$

and disparate impact given by

$$DI(F') = DI(F) - P(X \in Q(c_G))/P(X \in \mathcal{B}) \quad (87)$$

if group b is still disadvantaged in F' (i.e. $DI(F) \geq P(X \in Q(c_G))/P(X \in \mathcal{B})$), and otherwise

$$|DI(F) - DI(F')| \leq P(X \in Q(c_G))/P(X \in \mathcal{B}). \quad (88)$$

PROOF.

F' and F only differ on the datapoints that are classified as 0 by F but as 1 by F' . These are the datapoints that have prediction < 0.5 by f but ≥ 0.5 by f' , i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} & \{x \in \mathcal{X} : \sigma^{-1}(f(x)) < 0 \wedge \sigma^{-1}(f'(x)) \geq 0\} \\ & = \{x \in \mathcal{B} : -c_G \leq \sigma^{-1}(f(x)) < 0\}. \end{aligned} \quad (89)$$

Now this set of points is $Q(c_G)$, and the maximum change in accuracy occurs if one model is right on all points, whereas the

other model is wrong on all points, and all predictions are as extreme as possible. Then, assuming that one of the models is calibrated on that set, the label ratio is bounded from both sides by $\sigma(-c_G) \leq P(Y | X \in Q(c_G)) \leq \sigma(c_G)$. This means the change in accuracy is bounded by $2 \cdot \sigma(c_G) \cdot P(X \in Q(c_G))$, giving us (86).

Recall that disparate impact is defined as

$$DI(F) = |P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}) - P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B})|. \quad (90)$$

Now only predictions on group b are changed, such that

$$P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}) = P(F'(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}). \quad (91)$$

On the other hand, we have

$$P(F'(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B}) = P(\{F(X) = 1 \vee -c_G \leq \sigma^{-1}(f(x)) < 0 | X \in \mathcal{B}\}), \quad (92)$$

and thus

$$P(F'(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B}) = P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B}) + P(X \in Q(c_G))/P(X \in \mathcal{B}). \quad (93)$$

Putting things together, we get

$$|P(F'(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}) - P(F'(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B})| \quad (94)$$

$$= |P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{A}) - P(F(X) = 1 | X \in \mathcal{B})| - P(X \in Q(c_G))/P(X \in \mathcal{B}) \quad (95)$$

if the terms inside the vertical bars remain positive. Otherwise, we still get (88). \square